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PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORT AS A SOCIAL PHENOMENON

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ANNOTATION

This article provides detailed information that physical culture and sports are the most important social phenomena in human life. Sport is not only a sphere that acquaints the whole world with this person, nation, state, but also serves to form each person as a healthy person, both physically and spiritually mature. Information is also provided on ongoing reforms in the field of sports development in our country.

Key words: physical education, sport, social phenomenon, physical health, spiritual maturity, well-being, sport as a social phenomenon.

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ФИЗИЧЕСКОЕ ВОСПИТАНИЕ И СПОРТ КАК СОЦИАЛЬНОЕ ЯВЛЕНИЕ**АННОТАЦИЯ**

В данной статье представлена подробная информация о том, что физическая культура и спорт являются важнейшими социальными явлениями в жизни человека. Спорт – это не только сфера, знакомящая весь мир с этим человеком, нацией, государством, но и служащая формированию каждого человека как здоровой личности, как физически, так и духовно зрелой. Также представлена информация о проводимых реформах в области развития спорта в нашей стране.

Ключевые слова: физическое воспитание, спорт, социальное явление, физическое здоровье, духовная зрелость, благополучие, спорт как социальное явление.

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JISMONIY TARBIYA VA SPORT IJTIMOIY HODISA OLARAK

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada jismoniy tarbiya va sport inson hayotidagi eng muhim ijtimoiy hodisa ekanligi haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan. Sport nafaqat bu inson, millat, davlat bilan butun dunyoni oshno qiluvchi soha, balki har bir insonni sog'lom, ham jismonan, ham ma'naviy yetuk shaxs sifatida shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi. Shuningdek, mamlakatimizda sportni rivojlantirish borasida amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar haqida ham ma'lumotlar berildi.

Kalit so'zlar: jismoniy tarbiya, sport, ijtimoiy hodisa, jismoniy salomatlik, ma'naviy kamolot, farovonlik, sport ijtimoiy hodisa sifatida.

In connection with the implementation of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" all segments of the population, especially, to create modern conditions for regular physical culture and sports of the younger generation, to strengthen the confidence of young people in sports through sports competitions, to develop courage, patriotism, devotion to the motherland, as well as to develop talented athletes among young people. It is gratifying, of course, that large-scale work is being done to improve the selection system and, in general, to further develop physical culture and sports.

Sport is not only the basis of physical and mental health, but also a means of protecting young people who enter life with high hopes from various harmful foreign ideas and habits, giving them the full realization of their abilities and talents. Therefore, in recent years, our country has signed a number of legal and regulatory documents in this regard. On June 3, 2017, the Resolution "On measures to further develop physical culture and mass sports", on March 5, 2018, the Decree "On measures to radically improve the state system in the field of physical culture and sports" and according to this decree and the transformation of the sports committee into a ministry, as well as Adoption of Resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of January 29, 2019 "On promotion of healthy lifestyles and involvement of the population in physical and mass sports in Uzbekistan", February 13, 2019, "On approval of the Concept of development of physical and mass sports in Uzbekistan for 2019-2023" It marks the beginning of a new stage in the field of physical culture and sports in Uzbekistan. In his Address to the Oliy Majlis on December 29, 2018, President Mirziyoyev said: "We will continue to attach great importance to the accelerated development of sports, encouragement and support of athletes who have achieved high results in international competitions. In order to promote sports among our younger generation, we will establish sports schools for children and adolescents in the most remote areas", he said.

Physical culture is an integral part of human culture, its separate field. However, this specific process is formed as a result of human activity, the means and method of physical improvement of the individual. Physical culture affects aspects of life that are perceived in the form of a person's tendencies, which are genetically transmitted and develop in the course of life under the influence of upbringing, activity, and the environment. Sport as an important social phenomenon is widespread at all levels of modern society, has a broad impact on key areas of public life [1]. Sports and physical education affect people's national relations, social life, status, shape a modern lifestyle, moral values, help to change people's lifestyles in a positive way.

Physical culture is, by its very nature, a process of optimizing the necessary skills and abilities, physical abilities, health status and performance, with targeted action in the form of exercise that allows for effective movement. Sport, as a model of the social factor, repeats the alternative to modern culture, preserves and strengthens the important mechanisms of human socio-cultural life, the transition to a subculture of the individual, shaping him as a socially harmonious person. Sport is a powerful type of activity through which one can determine one's personal development and shape one's lifestyle [2].

Indeed, the sports phenomenon has a strong socialization. Sport is a unique ideology that can unite the society, the individual with the national idea, serves the people's desire for success and

victory. In addition, modern sports, which perform many social functions, are multifunctional and multifaceted. Physical education and sports, first of all, from strengthening health, educating the younger generation in the country to distract them from harmful influences, meet the demand for street and entertainment services, provide economic incentives, protect the honor of the country, form patriotism and so on. [3].

Thus, considering sports as a social phenomenon is an important event in the education of student youth. The condition for the formation of the subject of social problems is sport. It is important to increase the methodological and theoretical problems of sports as a social institution in the life of the individual and society, especially the student-athlete, as well as people's interest in sports.

Physical culture as an integral part of the general culture and professional training of students in higher education is a humanitarian component of education, which is manifested through the combination of spiritual and physical strength, the formation of universal values such as health, physical and mental well-being, physical perfection. Physical education and sports organically complement the huge integrative and communicative potential available in the activities of young people and any human social activity.

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